

Decarbonation-rehydration characteristics of Almora magnesite under equilibrium condition

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Abstract : Decarbonation-rehydration study of Almora magnesite carries a great practical significance in preparing different magnesia products, predicting the structure-property relationship of the high magnesia bearing ore for its effective utilization and controlling the drying-firing schedule of magnesite based ceramics. This paper describes a comprehensive thermal decarbonation-rehydration behavior of naturally occurring Indian magnesite in powder form from Almora region relation to variation of thermal treatment temperature, time of rehydration and relative humidity of the environment.

Keywords : Magnesite, heat treatment, decarbonation-rehydration, relative humidity.

Introduction

The decarbonation-rehydration behavior of naturally occurring divalent carbonate minerals such as calcite, magnesite, dolomite on progressive heat treatment offers a powerful tool in ascertaining the degree of reversibility of decarbonation-rehydration reaction, changes in crystallographic forms, grain morphology and reactivity of decarbonated or rehydrated products as a function of decomposition temperature, rehydration time and relative humidity of the environment. Magnesite is composed essentially of magnesium carbonate ($MgCO_3$). It forms continuous isomorphic series with siderite ($FeCO_3$), calcium carbonate ($CaCO_3$) and manganese carbonate ($MnCO_3$) and associated with impurities like silica and alumina. Magnesite belongs to trigonal $R\bar{3}c$, system having cell dimensions; $a : 4.637 \text{ \AA}$, $c : 15.023 \text{ \AA}$ and $Z : 6^1$. Magnesite is the principal raw material for steel making basic refractories. Magnesite ore when calcined is converted into different grades of magnesia with evolution of CO_2 . Depending on thermal treatment condition, magnesite transforms into four types of products namely caustic calcined magnesite, hard burnt magnesite, dead burnt magnesite and fused magnesite. Magnesite is used as an important refractory in the metallurgy of copper, lead and nickel, for electric arc furnace, convertors, tundish vessels in the

steel metallurgy, in preparation of oxychloride or Sorel cement, fire proof paint, metallic magnesium; magnesium chloride and magnesium sulphate.

The dehydration-rehydration studies of kaolinite clays at different temperatures and relative humidities had shown that maximum mass loss takes place mostly in the temperature zone of 400–600 °C due to the loss of structural water. Even after heating at 800 °C, the clay sample retains some residual water in the structure, which is intrinsically related to the collapse of layer lattice structure of kaolinitic clay during heat treatment. Furthermore, mass gain due to rehydration of the dehydrated clay sample is ascribed to the dehydration temperature and relative humidity of the environment². The results for the citric acid test for reactivity, surface area analyses and extend of hydration of the MgO samples calcined at different temperatures shows that reactivity of magnesite decreases as a inverse function of calcination temperature³.

Decarbonation-rehydration reactions of bivalent carbonate have attracted special attention of scientists since these reactions are likely to govern the nature and quality of product.

The present investigation deals with careful study of decarbonation-rehydration behavior of magnesite of Indian origin from Almora region with respect to variation

of heat treatment temperature, time of rehydration and relative humidity of the environment.

Experimental

Naturally occurring Almora magnesite (India) has been chosen as the starting material for the thermal decomposition study. The bulk sample in the lump form was at first ground to fine powder, sieved into (-60 + 120) BS mesh, dried at 110 °C and stored in desiccators. The finely agated sample was chemically analyzed with respect to chemical constituents following standard method of ore analysis. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) analysis of magnesite powder was recorded by a Perkin-Elmer-783 instrument in KBr phase in the frequency region 400–4000 cm^{-1} for isolating the nature of bond. For identification of crystal-line phases in Almora magnesite, X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of the sample was carried out using Phillips automatic X-ray diffractometer (X'Pert PRO PW-3071) with Ni filtered Cu-K α radiation of 1.5405 Å at a scanning rate of 2.0°/min. The microstructure of Almora magnesite was studied using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (ZEISS, INCA Penta EETX3, MODEL.EDS8100, UK). The thermal behavior of the sample was examined by differential thermal analysis (TG-DTA) using NETZCH simultaneous thermal analyzer (STA409) at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The mass loss due to decomposition of Almora magnesite was recorded by taking a definite weight (0.5 g) of the magnesite sample in porcelain crucible and heat treated at different temperatures from 200–900 °C at an interval of 100 °C for 2 h in an electric muffle furnace respectively.

After measuring the decomposition loss at a particular temperature, the gain in mass due to rehydration of each heat treated sample due to rehydration was recorded successively at 35%, 57%, 75% and 100% relative humidities for the period of 24 h, 48 h, 72 h and 96 h respectively.

Since the magnitude of rehydration at given temperature is dependent on the amount of CO₂ lost during its decomposition process, the percentage of rehydration of each heat treated sample was measured by $(R/D) \times 100$ where, R = mass gain due to rehydration on the basis of decarbonated weight of same sample after heat treatment and D = decarbonated weight.

Results and discussion

Basically Almora magnesite has trigonal R3c structure. It is brownish white primarily due to presence of iron oxide. The physico-chemical properties of Almora magnesite sample are presented in Table 1. The typical chemical analysis of raw magnesite sample indicates that Almora magnesite is composed of high magnesia content in association with substantial calcia and low percentage of alumina, iron oxide and silica.

Table 1. Physico-chemical analysis of Almora magnesite

Chemical constituents	% (w/w)
MgO	41.85
CaO	4.37
Al ₂ O ₃	0.62
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.25
SiO ₂	0.6
L.O.I.	52.29
Texture	Hard, brownish white in appearance
Loose bulk density	1.61 g/cc
Specific surface area	0.9224 m ² /g

The L.O.I. value of 52.29 wt% is closely consistent with that of pure MgCO₃ indicating better quality of Almora magnesite⁴. Moderate loose bulk density and surface area values of magnesite powder depicted its fine particle size fraction.

In magnesite mineral, mostly OH stretching, OH bending vibrations CO₃²⁻ stretching and bending vibration give rise to IR absorption spectra. Broad FTIR bands (Fig. 1) at around 3576.01, 3575.84 and 3440.88 cm^{-1} is due to presence of bound water while appearance of IR spectra at 3050.58, 2534.33, 2918.13 and 1827.44 cm^{-1} correspond to the presence of organic matter. The bands at 2918.13, 1827.44 and 1450 cm^{-1} are assigned to asymmetric stretching vibration of CO₃²⁻. CO₃²⁻ symmetric stretching vibration occurs at 1022.68 cm^{-1} . The out-of-plane bending modes for CO₃²⁻ are visible in the wavenumber range of 885.47 cm^{-1} , 855.35 cm^{-1} show CO₃²⁻ bending vibration. Intense FTIR absorption peaks at 747.90 cm^{-1} is assigned to the in-plane bending vibration of carbonate ion^{4,5}.

Phase analysis by X-ray diffraction :

Powder XRD pattern of Almora magnesite showed sharp characteristic peaks of magnesite and siderite crystals and small peak of dolomite phase.

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of Almora magnesite sample.

Fig 2. Powder XRD pattern of Almora magnesite powder.

The slight peak shift and strong relative intensity of peaks may probably be related to the solid solution of magnesium carbonate, siderite and dolomite phases⁶.

Microstructure by SEM study :

The SEM micrograph of Almora magnesite exhibits a distribution of elongated fine grains in the size range of 0.5–3 micrometers in the meandering veins of varying thickness.

Thermal behavior of magnesite focuses mainly on the mineralogical phase composition, the impurity level and

Fig. 3. SEM micrograph of Almora magnesite.

crystallinity of the sample. The TG-DSC curve of Almora magnesite (Fig. 4) shows the presence of three endothermic peaks at 120 °C, 620 °C and 690 °C respectively. The 1st peak at 120 °C corresponds to removal of hydroxyl water. The major peak at 620 °C is due to decarbonation of magnesite and the small endothermic peak at 690 °C arising from decomposition of dolomite. The TGA curve exhibits a total mass loss of 52.18% in the temperature range studied which is closely matched with theoretical value of 52% for decomposition reaction of pure magnesite leading to the formation of magnesia with expulsion of CO₂ at elevated temperature according to the following equation :

MgO is ionic in nature, it possesses high hydration tendency. The structural stability and surface activity of basic MgO have been studied through the rehydration of decarbonated materials as shown in Figs. 6–8. The magnitude of rehydration increases initially with increasing heat treatment temperature, attains a maximum value at 600 °C for all humidities. Then it shows a gradual downward trend at 700 °C and above particularly during rehydration at lower R.H. of the environment.

From the analysis of curves, it is evident that in case of humidities from 35–75%, maximum rehydration occurs for sample previously decomposed at 600 °C while at saturated humidity maximum rehydration occurs with samples decomposed at 500 °C. Rehydration of decom-

Fig. 4. TG-DSC curve of Almora magnesite at the heating rate of 10 K min⁻¹.

A comprehensive thermal decarbonation curve of Almora magnesite powder against temperature of heat treatment powder up to 900 °C has been given in Fig. 5. The decarbonation curve is typically sigmoid in nature. From Fig. 5 it is apparent that the percent weight loss increases slowly up to 300 °C followed by a sharp rise up to 600 °C, then becomes flat above 700 °C. Maximum decomposition loss of 51.89% has been observed at 700 °C and onwards which corresponds to complete breakdown of crystal lattice of magnesite towards formation of periclase and loss of CO₂.

Rehydration of sample provides an important insight in connection with the reactivity of magnesia formed and gradual change in its adsorption capacity. Since derived

Fig. 5. Equilibrium dehydration-decarbonation of Almora magnesite sample against temperature.

Fig. 6. Mass gain due to rehydration of the decomposed magnesite powder at different relative humidities (1st day).

Fig. 9. Mass gain due to rehydration of the decomposed magnesite powder at different relative humidities (4th day).

Fig. 7. Mass gain due to rehydration of the decomposed magnesite powder at different relative humidities (2nd day).

Fig. 8. Mass gain due to rehydration of the decomposed magnesite powder at different relative humidities (3rd day).

posed precursor powder increases steadily up to 3rd day over which, it becomes almost constant. With samples dehydrated at lower temperature up to 300 °C, nominal rehydration take place from the physical adsorption of water. However, highest order of rehydration tendency in case of higher humidity and at saturated R.H. and upto 3rd day of rehydration for the magnesite sample decomposed at 500–600 °C occurs due to simultaneous occurrence of surface condensation, physical and chemical adsorption. The magnesite sample decomposed at 700 °C and onwards exhibit lesser rehydration tendency attributing to the reduction of surface activity of the derived magnesia.

Summary and conclusions

From the study, a very useful data on the thermal behavior of naturally occurring Almora magnesite with respect to temperature of heat treatment and time of rehydration is evolved which may be immensely utilized for preparation of active magnesia precursor, ascertaining the degree of reversibility and selecting the proper drying-firing schedule of magnesite based ceramic bodies.

Almora magnesite of Indian origin shows maximum mass loss in between 600–700 °C due to expulsion of CO₂. The simultaneous mass gain during rehydration of the decarbonated sample is also observed to depend very much on the decomposition temperature of the sample, time of rehydration and relative humidity of the environment. Strong rehydration affinity and ultra-reactivity of the magnesia derived at 600 °C is recorded within 3 days of rehydration and around 75% R.H. of the environment.

The higher order of surface reactivity of decarbonated magnesite in and around 600 °C is highly related to the ionic character, porous structure, finer particle sizes and large internal surface area of fully decarbonated magnesite.

Almora magnesite sample becomes more or less surface inert at 700 °C and above upto presence of 75% relative humidity of the environment.

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